

Reading Common Statistical Tables

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ABSTRACT

There are four commonly used statistical tables, namely Student's t , Unit Normal Distribution or Z, chi-square, and F tables. The purpose of this paper is to provide researchers and practitioners a brief description of the tables and how to use them. The T table is used for sample analysis with normal distribution. The Z table is used for population or expected value analysis with normal distribution. The chi square table is used for one sample analysis that is not normally distributed. The F table is used for two samples that are not normally distributed.

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1.0 READING STUDENT T TABLE

The Student t table is used for a single sample testing. The table is arranged by row and column with corresponding values for each row and column intersection point. The row is placed at the top of the table. The values in the first row of the table are the percentage confidence level (CI). The percentage on the top row include: 70, 75, 80, 87.5, 90, 97.5, 99 and 99.5%. This is the confidence level selected by the researcher. A common standard confidence interval used in social science is 95%.

The second set of indicator used in the t table is the degree of freedom. The degree of freedom in this table is defined as the number of observations minus one: $df = n - 1$ where df is degree of freedom and n is the number of observation or sample size.

How to read the t table? Assume one selects a confidence interval of 95%, find the column on the table where the first row is marked with 95 for 95%. Use this column for the reading. The second step is to move down the first column where it is marked df ; find the correct degree of freedom for your sample. The third step is to read across from df of the first column to the 95% CI column, where df and 0.95 intersects, this is the critical value call t -critical. For example using 95% confidence interval, with 10 observations the degree of freedom is $df = 9$. Reading the df and 95 column, the row from df and the column from 95 intersect at 1.83. The critical value for t is

1.83. This is the threshold value against which the observed critical value must be compared. The hypothesis statements may be framed, thus:

$$H_0 : t_{obs}(df, CI) < 1.83 \tag{1}$$

$$H_0 : t_{obs}(df, CI) \geq 1.83 \tag{2}$$

The Student *t* distribution is given by:

$$t = \frac{\bar{X} - \mu}{S / \sqrt{n}} \tag{3}$$

where *t* = critical value of *t*; *S* = sample mean; *n* = sample size; and μ = population mean.

In practice, the Student *t* table is commonly used for two sample means comparison. For instance, if we are provided with the high and low prices of SP500 for 10 days, are the difference in the high and low prices significant different? In order to answer this question, the T-test for the paired mean difference may be used:

$$t = \frac{\bar{d}}{S_d / \sqrt{n}} \tag{4}$$

Table 1 below shows the t-test under (4) is accomplished.

Table 1: Statistical test for dBar analysis

Item	High	Low	$d_i = hi - lo$	$\bar{d}$	S_d
1	2,085.06	2,071.02	14.04	17.19	9.17
2	2,082.78	2,067.00	15.78		
3	2,074.28	2,056.32	17.96		
4	2,098.63	2,056.64	41.99		
5	2,108.92	2,095.38	13.54		
6	2,116.04	2,101.78	14.26		
7	2,125.10	2,108.58	16.52		
8	2,128.03	2,119.89	8.14		
9	2,129.87	2,112.50	17.37		
10	2,121.64	2,109.38	12.26		

Using equation (4): $t = \frac{\bar{d}}{S_d / \sqrt{n}} = \frac{17.19}{9.17 / \sqrt{10}} = \frac{17.19}{9.17 / 3.16} = \frac{17.19}{2.90} = 5.92$. The critical value for the

difference between the low and high price is 5.92. This value is called t(observed); it must be compared to the critical value from the Student *t* Table. In this example, we have 10 items. When $n=10$ the degree of freedom is $df=9$. The critical value at 9 degrees of freedom for 95% confidence interval is 1.83. this value “1.83” is read from the Student *t* Table. Move down from *df* column and read across to intersect column whose first row is marked 95, the intersection gives the value: 1.83.

Figure 1: Read Student *t* Critical Value

df	Percentile Point								
	70	75	80	87.5	90	95	97.5	99	99.5
1	0.73	1.00	1.38	2.41	3.08	6.31	12.71	31.82	63.66
2	0.62	0.81	1.06	1.60	1.89	2.92	4.30	6.96	9.92
3	0.58	0.79	0.98	1.42	1.64	2.35	3.18	4.54	5.84
4	0.57	0.77	0.94	1.34	1.53	2.13	2.78	3.75	4.60
5	0.56	0.75	0.92	1.30	1.48	2.02	2.57	3.36	4.03
6	0.55	0.74	0.91	1.27	1.44	1.94	2.45	3.14	3.71
7	0.55	0.73	0.90	1.25	1.42	1.89	2.36	3.00	3.50
8	0.55	0.72	0.89	1.24	1.40	1.86	2.31	2.90	3.36
9	0.54	0.71	0.88	1.23	1.38	1.83	2.26	2.82	3.25
10	0.54	0.70	0.88	1.22	1.37	1.81	2.23	2.76	3.17

1.2 Numerical Illustrations of Various T-Tests

There are many types of T-tests. The following provides samples of various T-tests. The method of reading the Student *t* Table follows the same procedures explained above.

There are cases where the variances of two samples are unknown and unequal; this case requires a unique T-test of its own. This T-test requires two samples where their distribution curves are difference; hence, unequal variance. Since, these variances are different, they are also unequal. The test is given by:

$$T = \frac{(\bar{x}_1 - \bar{x}_2) - (\mu_1 - \mu_2)}{\sqrt{\frac{s_1^2}{n_1} + \frac{s_2^2}{n_2}}} \quad (5)$$

where $s_1^2 = \frac{1}{n_1 - 1} \sum_{i=1}^{n_1} (x_{1i} - \bar{x}_1)^2$ and $s_2^2 = \frac{1}{n_2 - 1} \sum_{i=1}^{n_2} (x_{2i} - \bar{x}_2)^2$. This is used when we have two samples with unequal length of data string.

Suppose we take the low and high price and subject these two arrays to the tes under equation (5). Let the high price be X_1 and low price be X_2 . The mean for X_1 is $\bar{x}_1 = 2107.04$ with variance $s_1^2 = 422.36$ and estimated mean of $\mu_1 = 2095.99$. The mean for X_2 is $\bar{x}_1 = 2089.85$ with variance $s_2^2 = 602.71$ and estimated mean of $\mu_2 = 2076.65$. Both arrays have the same length of data string $n_1 = n_2 = 10$. Now applying equation (5):

$$\begin{aligned} T &= \frac{(\bar{x}_1 - \bar{x}_2) - (\mu_1 - \mu_2)}{\sqrt{\frac{s_1^2}{n_1} + \frac{s_2^2}{n_2}}} = \frac{(2107.04 - 2089.85) - (2095.99 - 2076.65)}{\sqrt{\frac{422.36}{10} + \frac{602.71}{10}}} \\ &= \frac{17.19 - 19.34}{\sqrt{42.24 + 60.27}} = \frac{-2.15}{\sqrt{102.98}} = \frac{-2.15}{10.15} \\ &= |-0.2118| \\ &= 0.2118 \end{aligned}$$

The observed t-value is 0.2118. This value is compared to the critical t-value in the Student *t* Table. For 9 degrees of freedom, the critical value for 95% CI is 1.83. The difference between the high and low prices is not significant. Note that this conclusion differs from that reached under

equation (4). There, the unit of analysis was the difference of their values. Here, the unit of analysis is the original value itself.

Another situation may involved two samples with variances unknown but equal:

$$T = \frac{(\bar{x}_1 - \bar{x}_2) - (\mu_1 - \mu_2)}{S \sqrt{\frac{1}{n_1} + \frac{1}{n_2}}} \quad (6)$$

where $S = \sqrt{S^2}$. The variance is defined as:

$$S^2 = \frac{(SS_1 + SS_2)}{(n_1 + n_2 - 2)} \text{ where } SS_1 = \sum_{i=1}^{n_1} (x_{1i} - \bar{x}_1)^2 \text{ and } SS_2 = \sum_{i=1}^{n_2} (x_{2i} - \bar{x}_2)^2 .$$

We first calculate the sum squared difference for each array. The calculations yield $SS_1 = 3801.26$ and $SS_2 = 5424.42$. The pool variance is $S^2 = (3801.26 + 5424.42) / 10 + 10 - 2 = 9225.68 / 18 = 512.54$; thus, the standard pool deviation is 22.64. The calculation under equation (6) follows:

$$\begin{aligned} T &= \frac{(\bar{x}_1 - \bar{x}_2) - (\mu_1 - \mu_2)}{S \sqrt{\frac{1}{n_1} + \frac{1}{n_2}}} = \frac{(2107.04 - 2089.85) - (2095.99 - 2076.65)}{22.64 \sqrt{\frac{1}{10} + \frac{1}{10}}} \\ &= \frac{17.19 - 19.34}{22.64 \sqrt{0.20}} \\ &= \frac{-2.15}{22.64(0.4472)} = \frac{-2.15}{10.12} \\ &= |-0.2125| \\ &= 0.2125 \end{aligned}$$

The conclusion is the two samples are not statistically different. The critical value from the Student *t* Table is 1.83 for 9 degrees of freedom.

The third commonly employed T-test is the test for statistical significance of the correlation between the dependent and independent variables in the predictive function: $Y = a + bX$. This T-test involves two steps: (i) calculate the correlation coefficient *r* and (ii) use the T_r equation to verify the significance of the relationship between X and Y via the value of *b*. The correlation coefficient is given by:

$$r = b \left(\frac{S_x}{S_y} \right) \quad (7)$$

where *r* = Pearson correlation coefficient; S_x = standard deviation of the independent variable X_i ; and S_y = standard deviation of dependent variable Y_i . The second step is to use the T-test for correlation coefficient to verify the significance of the relationship between X_i and Y_i :

$$T_r = \frac{r\sqrt{n-2}}{\sqrt{(1-r^2)}} \quad (8)$$

In the example above, we can test whether the high price or low price has any relationship with the close price for SP500 in the designated 10 days of trading. Step 1, we need to run a regression of high price against the close price and regress low price against close price. We should have two linear equations with separate slopes b_1 and b_2 to test. Table 2 below illustrates the data set that we will use.

Table 2: Data set to illustrate linear regression

Item	High = X1	Low = X2	Close = Y
1	2,085.06	2,071.02	2,076.78
2	2,082.78	2,067.00	2,077.42
3	2,074.28	2,056.32	2,063.11
4	2,098.63	2,056.64	2,057.64
5	2,108.92	2,095.38	2,101.49
6	2,116.04	2,101.78	2,102.31
7	2,125.10	2,108.58	2,108.58
8	2,128.03	2,119.89	2,124.20
9	2,129.87	2,112.50	2,122.85
10	2,121.64	2,109.38	2,109.99

If we use manual calculation to derive the terms for a linear regression, the following steps are used:

$$\begin{aligned}
 I &= N \sum XY - (\sum X)(\sum Y) \\
 II &= N \sum X^2 - (\sum X)^2 \\
 III &= N \sum Y^2 - (\sum Y)^2
 \end{aligned} \quad (9)$$

To find the slope of the line:

$$b = \frac{I}{II} \quad (10)$$

The intercept is given by:

$$a = \bar{Y} - b\bar{X} \quad (11)$$

The forecast error:

$$c = \sqrt{\left[\frac{1}{N(N-2)} \right] \left[(III) - \frac{(I)^2}{(II)} \right]} \quad (12)$$

Using SSP program, the regression for the high and close price is steps (9) – (12) may be done quickly. The result is shown in Figure 2.

Figure 2: Regression between Close and High Price

Simple Regression				
Average value of the dependent variable Close:		2,094.4370		
Average value of the explanatory variable High:		2,107.0350		
Number of observations:		10		
The least squares estimates of the equation $Y = a + bX + e$:				
variable	coefficient	std. error	t value	one-sided p value
intercept	-109.8305	386.5385	0.2841	0.3918
High	1.0461	0.1834	5.7028	0.0002
standard error of estimate (SEE):		11.3101		
coefficient of determination (R-squared):		0.8026		

The predictive function is $-109.83 + 1.04X$ with correlation coefficient of $r = 0.8026$ and the T-critical value of 5.70 compared to the standard critical value of 1.83. According to this result, there is a positive correlation between the high and close price. This relationship is verified as statistically significant.

The second test is the low price and the close price. The result of the regression is illustrated in figure 3.

Figure 3: Regression between Close and Low Price

Simple Regression				
Average value of the dependent variable Close:		2,094.4370		
Average value of the explanatory variable Low:		2,089.8490		
Number of observations:		10		
The least squares estimates of the equation $Y = a + bX + e$:				
variable	coefficient	std. error	t value	one-sided p value
intercept	78.3536	116.6936	0.6714	0.2604
Low	0.9647	0.0558	17.2778	0.0000
standard error of estimate (SEE):		4.1123		
coefficient of determination (R-squared):		0.9739		

The predictive function is $Y = 78.35 + 0.96X$ with critical t-value of 17.28 and correlation coefficient of 0.97. In both cases, we cannot verify the significance of r until we employed equation (8). Our calculation follows:

$$T_{r(hi)} = \frac{r\sqrt{n-2}}{\sqrt{(1-r^2)}} = \frac{0.8026\sqrt{10-2}}{\sqrt{(1-0.8026)^2}} = \frac{0.8026\sqrt{8}}{\sqrt{(0.1974)^2}} = \frac{0.8026(2.83)}{\sqrt{0.04}} = \frac{2.27}{0.20} = 11.35$$

The strength of the relationship between the close price (dependent variable) and the high price (independent variable) is statistically significant. It has the T_r value of 11.35 compared to the standard threshold value under 95% confidence interval is 1.83.

We next conduct the same test for the relationship between the close price and the low price.

$$T_{r(lo)} = \frac{r\sqrt{n-2}}{\sqrt{(1-r^2)}} = \frac{0.97\sqrt{10-2}}{\sqrt{(1-0.97)^2}} = \frac{0.97\sqrt{8}}{\sqrt{(0.03)^2}} = \frac{0.97(2.83)}{\sqrt{0.0009}} = \frac{2.75}{0.03} = 91.67$$

Similarly, we found that the T-value is 91.67. This value is higher than the threshold value of 1.83. The relationship here is also significant.

2.0 READING THE UNIT NORMAL DISTRIBUTION OR Z TABLE

Given a series of observations $X_i : (x_1, x_2, \dots, x_n)$ with distribution $F(x)$, generally we assume that the data set is distributed normally (Beyer, 1971, Popoulis, 1984; Spiegel, 1992; Whittaker and Robinson, 1967), such that the probability distribution function may be given as:

$$f(x | \mu, \sigma) = \frac{1}{\sigma\sqrt{2\pi}} \exp\left[-\frac{(x-\mu)^2}{2\sigma^2}\right] \quad (13)$$

where μ is the expected population mean and σ is the expected population standard deviation; both may be estimated by:

$$\mu = x_i - t\left(\frac{S}{\sqrt{n}}\right) \quad (14)$$

Recall that the t-critical value for data distribution is given by:

$$t = \frac{x_i - \mu}{S/\sqrt{n}} \quad \text{see (3)}$$

It is from (3) that (14) is derived via algebraic arrangement. In similarly fashion, the estimated population distribution is obtained through the Z-equation of the unit normal distribution:

$$Z = \frac{x_i - \mu}{\sigma/\sqrt{n}} \quad (15)$$

Through algebraic arrangement, the estimated population standard deviation σ is given as:

$$\sigma = \left(\frac{\bar{x} - \mu}{Z}\right)\sqrt{n} \quad (16)$$

The percentage probability for each event is given by the standard score equation:

$$Z = \frac{X_i - \bar{X}}{S} \quad (17)$$

A numerical illustration is in order. Assume that we are given the following data.

Table 3: Data set to be used for the Z test

Date	Close
Jul 2, 2015	2,076.78
Jul 1, 2015	2,077.42
Jun 30, 2015	2,063.11
Jun 29, 2015	2,057.64
Jun 26, 2015	2,101.49
Jun 25, 2015	2,102.31
Jun 24, 2015	2,108.58
Jun 23, 2015	2,124.20
Jun 22, 2015	2,122.85
Jun 19, 2015	2,109.99

Source: <https://www.google.com/finance/historical?q=INDEXSP:.INX>
 Accessed: July 3, 2015.

The numbers in the column marked: “Close” is the value for SP500 daily index for 10 days. Thus, the sample size is $n = 10$. Using equation (2), the Z-critical for each event may be calculated as illustrated by the table below.

Table 4: Calculating the standard score

Item	X_i	$\bar{X}$	S	Z	F(Z)
1	2,076.78	2,094.44	24	-0.74	0.2266
2	2,077.42	2,094.44	24	-0.71	0.2266
3	2,063.11	2,094.44	24	-1.31	0.0885
4	2,057.64	2,094.44	24	-1.53	0.0606
5	2,101.49	2,094.44	24	0.29	0.6140
6	2,102.31	2,094.44	24	0.33	0.6290
7	2,108.58	2,094.44	24	0.59	0.7220
8	2,124.20	2,094.44	24	1.24	0.8930
9	2,122.85	2,094.44	24	1.18	0.8810
10	2,109.99	2,094.44	24	0.65	0.7420

The Z value is obtained through equation (17). The percentage probability F(Z) is obtained by reading from the Z-table. The Z-table is listed in 2-columns format. The first column is the Z-score or the standard score determined by equation (2). The second column is the area under the curve known as $1 - \alpha$ or the confidence interval. For example, item 10 has a Z-score of 0.65. Go to the Z-table and look for 0.65 in the column marked: $Z_{1-\alpha}$ where $Z_{1-\alpha} = 0.65$ the corresponding percentage probability is 0.742 or $1 - \alpha = 0.742$ or 74.2% chance. The hypothesis statements are: $H_0 : Z_{1-\alpha} < 1.65$ where 1.65 is the standard score for $1 - \alpha = 0.95$ or 95% confidence interval. The alternative hypothesis is $H_A : Z_{1-\alpha} \geq 1.65$. In this case, the result shows that the observed value is $1 - \alpha = 0.742$; thus, the price at 2,109.99 on June 19, 2015 lies within the confidence interval. Therefore, it is not consider high or low in relations to the mean price for the 10 days. In this case, the null hypothesis cannot be rejected. The alternative hypothesis is incorrect.

3.0 READING THE CHI SQUARE TABLE

A Chi square test is used when the data is not normally distributed. A data is not normally distributes because the sample is too small, or the nature of the data is non-normally distribute. When a data set is chi square distribute due to small sample size, the distribution will approximate normal distribution as n approaches infinity. The function of the Chi square table is to compare the

observed chi square test value with the assumed normal distribution *had the data set been normally distributed*. This is known as best fitting. Generally, chi square test is written as:

$$\chi^2 = \sum_{i=1}^k \frac{(O_i - E_i)^2}{E_i} \quad (18)$$

where O_i = observed frequency; and E_i = expected frequency. This approach is not meaningful. A more specific formal statement for test statistic under chi square is given as:

$$\chi^2 = \frac{(n-1)S^2}{\sigma^2} \quad (19)$$

This statement is the illustration of how the distribution is best fitted by comparing the observed variance with the estimated population variance. It answers the questions of “*had the data been normally distributed, would this current data set fit into the assumed normal distribution curve? How best does fit into the assumed normal distribution curve?*”

Recall our example data for 10 days of SP500 trading. Use the close price as the unit of analysis. The sample variance is $S^2 = 575.95$ and the population estimated variance is $\sigma^2 = 611.38$. The population variance is obtained through the use of equation (16). Using the chi square equation, the best fit could be verified, thus:

$$\chi^2 = \frac{(n-1)S^2}{\sigma^2} = \frac{(10-1)575.95}{611.38} = \frac{9(575.95)}{611.38} = \frac{5183.55}{611.38} = 8.48$$

The observed chi square is $\chi_{obs}^2 = 8.48$. Now go to the chi square table to read the critical value of the theoretical chi square value. The chi square table is provided in the same manner as the Student *t* Table. The reading of the chi square table follows the same procedure: (i) locate the degree of freedom in the first column; (ii) read across horizontally and find the threshold value for chi square at 95% CI column. In this case, $n = 10$. The degree of freedom is $df = 10 - 1 = 9$. At 9 degrees of freedom, the corresponding value at 95% CI is 16.90. The reading of the chi table is illustrated in the Figure 4 below.

Figure 4 Reading Chi Square Table

df	Percentile Point						
	50	75	90	95	97.5	99	99.5
1	0.46	1.30	2.70	3.80	5.00	6.60	7.90
2	1.40	2.80	4.60	6.00	7.40	9.20	10.60
3	2.40	4.10	6.30	7.80	9.40	11.30	12.80
4	3.40	5.40	7.80	9.50	11.10	13.30	14.90
5	4.40	6.60	9.20	11.10	12.80	15.10	16.70
6	5.40	7.80	10.60	12.60	14.40	16.80	18.50
7	6.40	9.00	12.00	14.10	16.00	18.50	20.30
8	7.30	10.20	13.40	15.50	17.50	20.10	22.00
9	8.30	11.40	14.70	16.90	19.00	21.70	23.60
10	9.30	12.50	16.00	18.30	20.50	23.20	25.20

The theoretical value or threshold value at 95% CI in the chi square table is 16.90. The hypothesis statements are: $H_0 : \chi_{9,95}^2 < 16.90$ and $H_A : \chi_{9,95}^2 \geq 16.90$. The result of the calculation under equation (19) shows that the observed value of chi square is $H_0 : \chi_{9,95}^2 = 8.48$. As the result, the null hypothesis cannot be rejected. What does it mean? It means that the data distribution of 10 observations does not produce significant dispersion outside of the assumed normal curve. In other words, the distribution of the observed data is found within the confidence interval of the assumed normal curve. Recall that the original assumption is that the sample size is small; therefore, the data is not normally distributed. Chi square test helps verify whether this *prima facie* conclusion of non-normality is valid by trying to fit the data distribution unto the normally distributed shape. The result shows that the observed data distribution may be fitted into the normal distribution curve. It is concluded that the so-called non-normality in the data distribution is not statistically significant. Therefore, for further testing, we could revert to the T-test and Z-test since the small data here still reside within the assumed normal distribution curve.

The explanation provided here deals with one sample that is assumed to have been non-normally distributed. As in section 1, we have seen two sample comparison study, in case of chi square there can also be two samples that are chi square distributed. In such a situation would chi square test be still valid? No, chi square test cannot accommodate a two non-normally distributed samples comparison study. To accomplish that task, we need to result to the F-test.

4.0 READING THE F TABLE

While there are there are Student *t* distribution for the T-table, Z distribution for the Z-table and chi square distribution for the chi square table, there is not F-distribution for the F-table. The f-table is used for comparing the difference ratio between two samples where one variance is S_1^2 from a sample size n_1 and degree of freedom of $d_1 = n - 1$ and another variance S_2^2 with degree of freedom of $d_2 = n_2 - 1$. This ratio analysis is called the F-test. The F-test is given by:

$$F = \frac{S_1^2}{S_2^2} \tag{20}$$

From our example of the high and low price, w can calculate the variance for each group. The variance for the high price is $S_1^2 = 422.36$ and the variance for the low price is $S_2^2 = 602.71$. Since we want to see a ration larger than 1.00, we will switch the order, thus: $S_1^2 = 602.71$ and $S_2^2 = 422.36$. Now the observed ratio under equation (20) is calculated as:

$$F = \frac{S_1^2}{S_2^2} = \frac{602.71}{422.36} = 1.43$$

This value is compared to the theoretical value in the F-table. The following decision rules applied: $H_0 : F_{d1/d2} < 3.18$ and $H_A : F_{d1/d2} \geq 3.18$.

The F-table is listed by degrees of freedom on both the column and row. Read the column and row degree of freedom and the value where both intersect is the theoretical threshold value. In this case, $d_1 = n_1 - 1 = 10 - 1 = 9$ and $d_2 = n_2 - 1 = 10 - 1 = 9$. In the F-table where 9 cross 9 degrees of freedom, the referenced value is 3.18. Figure 5 below illustrate how the F-table is read.

Figure 5 reading the F-Table

d1/d2	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9
1	161.40	199.50	215.70	224.60	230.20	234.00	236.80	238.90	240.50
2	18.51	19.00	19.16	19.25	19.30	19.33	19.35	19.37	19.38
3	10.13	9.55	9.28	9.12	9.01	8.94	8.89	8.85	8.81
4	7.71	6.94	6.59	6.39	6.26	6.16	6.09	6.04	6.00
5	6.61	5.79	5.41	5.19	5.05	4.95	4.88	4.82	4.77
6	5.99	5.14	4.76	4.53	4.39	4.28	4.21	4.15	4.10
7	5.59	4.74	4.35	4.12	3.97	3.87	3.79	3.73	3.68
8	5.32	4.46	4.07	3.84	3.69	3.58	3.50	3.44	3.39
9	5.12	4.26	3.86	3.63	3.48	3.37	3.29	3.23	3.18
10	4.96	4.10	3.71	3.48	3.33	3.22	3.14	3.07	3.02

There are other types of F-tests. However, all F-tests follow the same procedure on reading the threshold value in the F-table.

APPENDIX 1: Student t Table									
df	Percentile Point								
	70	75	80	87.5	90	95	97.5	99	99.5
1	0.73	1.00	1.38	2.41	3.08	6.31	12.71	31.82	63.66
2	0.62	0.81	1.06	1.60	1.89	2.92	4.30	6.96	9.92
3	0.58	0.79	0.98	1.42	1.64	2.35	3.18	4.54	5.84
4	0.57	0.77	0.94	1.34	1.53	2.13	2.78	3.75	4.60
5	0.56	0.75	0.92	1.30	1.48	2.02	2.57	3.36	4.03
6	0.55	0.74	0.91	1.27	1.44	1.94	2.45	3.14	3.71
7	0.55	0.73	0.90	1.25	1.42	1.89	2.36	3.00	3.50
8	0.55	0.72	0.89	1.24	1.40	1.86	2.31	2.90	3.36
9	0.54	0.71	0.88	1.23	1.38	1.83	2.26	2.82	3.25
10	0.54	0.70	0.88	1.22	1.37	1.81	2.23	2.76	3.17
11	0.54	0.70	0.88	1.21	1.36	1.80	2.20	2.72	3.11
12	0.54	0.69	0.87	1.21	1.36	1.78	2.18	2.68	3.05
13	0.54	0.69	0.87	1.21	1.35	1.77	2.16	2.65	3.01
14	0.54	0.69	0.87	1.20	1.34	1.76	2.14	2.62	2.98
15	0.54	0.69	0.87	1.20	1.34	1.75	2.13	2.60	2.95
16	0.54	0.69	0.86	1.20	1.34	1.75	2.12	2.58	2.92
17	0.53	0.69	0.86	1.19	1.33	1.74	2.11	2.57	2.90
18	0.53	0.69	0.86	1.19	1.33	1.73	2.10	2.50	2.88
19	0.53	0.69	0.86	1.19	1.33	1.73	2.09	2.54	2.86
20	0.53	0.69	0.86	1.18	1.32	1.72	2.09	2.53	2.85
21	0.53	0.69	0.86	1.18	1.32	1.72	2.08	2.52	2.83
22	0.53	0.69	0.86	1.18	1.32	1.72	2.07	2.51	2.82
23	0.53	0.68	0.86	1.18	1.32	1.71	2.07	2.50	2.81
24	0.53	0.68	0.86	1.18	1.32	1.71	2.06	2.49	2.80
25	0.53	0.68	0.86	1.18	1.32	1.71	2.06	2.49	2.79
26	0.53	0.68	0.86	1.18	1.32	1.71	2.06	2.48	2.79
27	0.53	0.68	0.86	1.18	1.31	1.70	2.05	2.47	2.78
28	0.53	0.68	0.86	1.17	1.31	1.70	2.05	2.47	2.77
29	0.53	0.68	0.85	1.17	1.31	1.70	2.05	2.46	2.76
30	0.53	0.68	0.85	1.17	1.31	1.70	2.04	2.46	2.75
40	0.53	0.68	0.85	1.17	1.30	1.68	2.02	2.42	2.70
50	0.53	0.67	0.85	1.16	1.30	1.68	2.01	2.40	2.68
60	0.53	0.67	0.85	1.16	1.30	1.67	2.00	2.39	2.66
80	0.53	0.67	0.85	1.16	1.29	1.66	1.99	2.37	2.64
100	0.53	0.67	0.84	1.16	1.29	1.66	1.98	2.36	2.63
200	0.52	0.67	0.84	1.15	1.29	1.65	1.97	2.35	2.60
500	0.52	0.67	0.84	1.15	1.28	1.65	1.96	2.33	2.59
<i>Infinity</i>	0.52	0.67	0.84	1.15	1.28	1.64	1.96	2.33	2.58

APPENDIX 2: Z- Table for Unit Normal Distribution

$Z_{1-\alpha}$	$1-\alpha$	$Z_{1-\alpha}$	$1-\alpha$	$Z_{1-\alpha}$	$1-\alpha$	$Z_{1-\alpha}$	$1-\alpha$
0.00	0.500	0.35	0.637	0.70	0.758	1.05	0.853
0.01	0.504	0.36	0.641	0.71	0.761	1.06	0.855
0.02	0.508	0.37	0.644	0.72	0.764	1.07	0.858
0.03	0.512	0.38	0.648	0.73	0.767	1.08	0.860
0.04	0.516	0.39	0.652	0.74	0.770	1.09	0.862
0.05	0.520	0.40	0.655	0.75	0.773	1.10	0.864
0.06	0.524	0.41	0.659	0.76	0.776	1.11	0.867
0.07	0.528	0.42	0.663	0.77	0.779	1.12	0.869
0.08	0.532	0.43	0.666	0.78	0.782	1.13	0.871
0.09	0.536	0.44	0.670	0.79	0.785	1.14	0.873
0.10	0.540	0.45	0.674	0.80	0.788	1.15	0.885
0.11	0.544	0.46	0.677	0.81	0.791	1.16	0.877
0.12	0.548	0.47	0.681	0.82	0.794	1.17	0.879
0.13	0.552	0.48	0.684	0.83	0.797	1.18	0.881
0.14	0.556	0.49	0.688	0.84	0.800	1.19	0.883
0.15	0.560	0.50	0.691	0.85	0.802	1.20	0.885
0.16	0.564	0.51	0.695	0.86	0.805	1.21	0.887
0.17	0.567	0.52	0.698	0.87	0.808	1.22	0.889
0.18	0.571	0.53	0.702	0.88	0.811	1.23	0.891
0.19	0.575	0.54	0.705	0.89	0.813	1.24	0.893
0.20	0.579	0.55	0.709	0.90	0.816	1.25	0.894
0.21	0.583	0.56	0.712	0.91	0.819	1.26	0.896
0.22	0.587	0.57	0.716	0.92	0.821	1.27	0.898
0.23	0.591	0.58	0.719	0.93	0.824	1.28	0.900
0.24	0.595	0.59	0.722	0.94	0.826	1.29	0.901
0.25	0.599	0.60	0.726	0.95	0.829	1.30	0.903
0.26	0.603	0.61	0.729	0.96	0.831	1.31	0.905
0.27	0.606	0.62	0.732	0.97	0.834	1.32	0.907
0.28	0.610	0.63	0.736	0.98	0.836	1.33	0.908
0.29	0.614	0.64	0.739	0.99	0.839	1.34	0.910
0.30	0.618	0.65	0.742	1.00	0.841	1.35	0.911
0.31	0.622	0.66	0.745	1.01	0.844	1.36	0.913
0.32	0.626	0.67	0.749	1.02	0.846	1.37	0.915
0.33	0.629	0.68	0.752	1.03	0.848	1.38	0.916
0.34	0.633	0.69	0.755	1.04	0.851	1.39	0.918

APPENDIX 2: Z- Table for Unit Normal Distribution, *continued*

$Z_{1-\alpha}$	$1-\alpha$	$Z_{1-\alpha}$	$1-\alpha$	$Z_{1-\alpha}$	$1-\alpha$	$Z_{1-\alpha}$	$1-\alpha$
1.40	0.919	1.75	0.960	2.10	0.982	2.45	0.993
1.41	0.921	1.76	0.961	2.11	0.983	2.46	0.993
1.42	0.922	1.77	0.962	2.12	0.983	2.47	0.993
1.43	0.924	1.78	0.962	2.13	0.983	2.48	0.993
1.44	0.925	1.79	0.963	2.14	0.984	2.49	0.994
1.45	0.926	1.80	0.964	2.15	0.984	2.50	0.994
1.46	0.928	1.81	0.965	2.16	0.985	2.51	0.994
1.47	0.929	1.82	0.966	2.17	0.985	2.52	0.994
1.48	0.931	1.83	0.966	2.18	0.985	2.53	0.994
1.49	0.932	1.84	0.967	2.19	0.986	2.54	0.994
1.50	0.933	1.85	0.968	2.20	0.986	2.55	0.995
1.51	0.934	1.86	0.969	2.21	0.986	2.56	0.995
1.52	0.936	1.87	0.969	2.22	0.987	2.57	0.995
1.53	0.937	1.88	0.970	2.23	0.987	2.58	0.995
1.54	0.938	1.89	0.971	2.24	0.987	2.59	0.995
1.55	0.939	1.90	0.971	2.25	0.988	2.60	0.9953
1.56	0.941	1.91	0.972	2.26	0.988		
1.57	0.942	1.92	0.973	2.27	0.988		
1.58	0.943	1.93	0.973	2.28	0.989	2.70	0.9965
1.59	0.944	1.94	0.974	2.29	0.989	2.80	0.9974
1.60	0.945	1.95	0.974	2.30	0.989	2.90	0.9981
1.61	0.946	1.96	0.975	2.31	0.990	3.00	0.9987
1.62	0.947	1.97	0.976	2.32	0.990	3.20	0.9993
1.63	0.948	1.98	0.976	2.33	0.990	3.40	0.9997
1.64	0.949	1.99	0.977	2.34	0.990	3.60	0.9998
1.65	0.950	2.00	0.977	2.35	0.991	3.80	0.99993
1.66	0.952	2.01	0.978	2.36	0.991	4.00	0.999968
1.67	0.953	2.02	0.978	2.37	0.991	4.50	0.999997
1.68	0.954	2.03	0.979	2.38	0.991	5.00	0.9999997
1.69	0.954	2.04	0.979	2.39	0.992	5.50	0.9999999
1.70	0.955	2.05	0.980	2.40	0.992		
1.71	0.956	2.06	0.980	2.41	0.992		
1.72	0.957	2.07	0.981	2.42	0.992		
1.73	0.958	2.08	0.981	2.43	0.992		
1.74	0.959	2.09	0.982	2.44	0.993		
1.645	0.950	2.326	0.990	3.090	0.999	3.891	0.99995
1.960	0.975	2.576	0.995	3.291	0.9999	4.417	0.999995

APPENDIX 3: Chi Square Table

<i>df</i>	Percentile Point						
	50	75	90	95	97.5	99	99.5
1	0.46	1.30	2.70	3.80	5.00	6.60	7.90
2	1.40	2.80	4.60	6.00	7.40	9.20	10.60
3	2.40	4.10	6.30	7.80	9.40	11.30	12.80
4	3.40	5.40	7.80	9.50	11.10	13.30	14.90
5	4.40	6.60	9.20	11.10	12.80	15.10	16.70
6	5.40	7.80	10.60	12.60	14.40	16.80	18.50
7	6.40	9.00	12.00	14.10	16.00	18.50	20.30
8	7.30	10.20	13.40	15.50	17.50	20.10	22.00
9	8.30	11.40	14.70	16.90	19.00	21.70	23.60
10	9.30	12.50	16.00	18.30	20.50	23.20	25.20
11	10.30	13.70	17.30	19.70	21.90	24.70	26.80
12	11.30	14.80	18.50	21.00	23.30	26.20	28.30
13	12.30	16.00	19.80	22.40	24.70	27.70	29.80
14	13.30	17.10	21.10	23.70	26.10	29.10	31.30
15	14.30	18.20	22.30	25.00	27.50	30.60	32.80
16	15.30	19.40	23.50	26.30	28.80	32.00	34.30
17	16.30	20.50	24.80	27.60	30.20	33.40	35.70
18	17.30	21.60	26.00	28.90	31.50	34.80	37.20
19	18.30	22.70	27.20	30.10	32.90	36.20	38.60
20	19.30	23.80	28.40	31.40	34.20	37.60	40.00
21	20.30	24.90	29.60	32.70	35.50	38.90	41.40
22	21.30	26.00	30.80	33.90	36.80	40.30	42.80
23	22.30	27.10	32.00	35.20	38.10	41.60	44.20
24	23.30	28.20	33.20	36.40	39.40	43.00	45.60
25	24.30	29.30	34.40	37.70	40.60	44.30	46.90
26	25.30	30.40	35.60	38.90	41.90	45.60	48.30
27	26.30	31.50	36.70	40.10	43.20	47.00	49.60
28	27.30	32.60	37.90	41.30	44.50	48.30	51.00
29	28.30	33.70	39.10	42.60	45.70	49.60	52.70
30	29.30	34.80	40.30	43.80	47.00	50.90	53.70
40	39.30	45.60	51.80	55.80	59.30	63.70	66.80
60	50.00	67.00	74.40	79.10	83.30	88.40	92.00
100	99.00	109.10	118.50	124.30	29.00	35.80	140.20

APPENDIX 4: F Table

d1 / d2	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9
1	161.40	199.50	215.70	224.60	230.20	234.00	236.80	238.90	240.50
2	18.51	19.00	19.16	19.25	19.30	19.33	19.35	19.37	19.38
3	10.13	9.55	9.28	9.12	9.01	8.94	8.89	8.85	8.81
4	7.71	6.94	6.59	6.39	6.26	6.16	6.09	6.04	6.00
5	6.61	5.79	5.41	5.19	5.05	4.95	4.88	4.82	4.77
6	5.99	5.14	4.76	4.53	4.39	4.28	4.21	4.15	4.10
7	5.59	4.74	4.35	4.12	3.97	3.87	3.79	3.73	3.68
8	5.32	4.46	4.07	3.84	3.69	3.58	3.50	3.44	3.39
9	5.12	4.26	3.86	3.63	3.48	3.37	3.29	3.23	3.18
10	4.96	4.10	3.71	3.48	3.33	3.22	3.14	3.07	3.02
11	4.84	3.98	3.59	3.36	3.20	3.09	3.01	2.95	2.90
12	4.75	3.89	3.49	3.26	3.11	3.00	2.91	2.85	2.80
13	4.67	3.81	3.41	3.18	3.03	2.92	2.83	2.77	2.71
14	4.60	3.74	3.34	3.11	2.96	2.85	2.76	2.70	2.65
15	4.54	3.68	3.29	3.06	2.90	2.79	2.71	2.64	2.59
16	4.49	3.63	3.24	3.01	2.85	2.74	2.66	2.59	2.54
17	4.45	3.59	3.20	2.96	2.81	2.70	2.61	2.55	2.49
18	4.41	3.55	3.16	2.93	2.77	2.66	2.58	2.51	2.46
19	4.38	3.52	3.13	2.90	2.74	2.63	2.54	2.48	2.42
20	4.35	3.49	3.10	2.87	2.71	2.60	2.51	2.45	2.39
21	4.32	3.47	3.07	2.84	2.68	2.57	2.49	2.42	2.37
22	4.30	3.44	3.05	2.82	2.66	2.55	2.46	2.40	2.34
23	4.28	3.42	3.03	2.80	2.64	2.53	2.44	2.37	2.32
24	4.26	3.40	3.01	2.78	2.62	2.51	2.42	2.36	2.30
25	4.24	3.39	2.99	2.76	2.60	2.49	2.40	2.34	2.28
26	4.23	3.37	2.98	2.74	2.59	2.47	2.39	2.32	2.27
27	4.21	3.35	2.96	2.73	2.57	2.46	2.37	2.31	2.25
28	4.20	3.34	2.95	2.71	2.56	2.45	2.36	2.29	2.24
29	4.18	3.33	2.93	2.70	2.55	2.43	2.35	2.28	2.22
30	4.17	3.32	2.92	2.69	2.53	2.42	2.33	2.27	2.21
40	4.08	3.23	2.84	2.61	2.45	2.34	2.25	2.18	2.12
60	4.00	3.15	2.76	2.53	2.37	2.25	2.17	2.10	2.04
120	3.92	3.07	2.68	2.45	2.29	2.17	2.09	2.02	1.96
Infinity	3.84	3.00	2.60	2.37	2.21	2.10	2.01	1.94	1.88

APPENDIX 4: F Table, continued

d1 / d2	10	12	15	20	24	30	40	60	120	Infinity
1	241.90	243.90	245.90	248.00	249.10	250.10	251.10	252.20	253.30	254.30
2	19.40	19.41	19.43	19.45	19.45	19.46	19.47	19.48	19.49	19.50
3	8.79	8.74	8.70	8.66	8.64	8.62	8.59	8.57	8.55	8.53
4	5.96	5.91	5.86	5.80	5.77	5.75	5.72	5.69	5.66	5.63
5	4.74	4.68	4.62	4.56	4.53	4.50	4.46	4.43	4.40	4.36
6	4.06	4.00	3.94	3.87	3.84	3.81	3.77	3.74	3.70	3.67
7	3.64	3.57	3.51	3.44	3.41	3.38	3.34	3.30	3.27	3.23
8	3.35	3.28	3.22	3.15	3.12	3.08	3.04	3.01	2.97	2.93
9	3.14	3.07	3.01	2.94	2.90	2.86	2.83	2.79	2.75	2.71
10	2.98	2.91	2.85	2.77	2.74	2.70	2.66	2.62	2.58	2.54
11	2.85	2.79	2.72	2.65	2.61	2.57	2.53	2.49	2.45	2.40
12	2.75	2.69	2.62	2.54	2.51	2.47	2.43	2.38	2.34	2.30
13	2.67	2.60	2.53	2.46	2.42	2.38	2.34	2.30	2.25	2.21
14	2.60	2.53	2.46	2.39	2.35	2.31	2.27	2.22	2.18	2.13
15	2.54	2.48	2.40	2.33	2.29	2.25	2.20	2.16	2.11	2.07
16	2.49	2.42	2.35	2.28	2.24	2.19	2.15	2.11	2.06	2.01
17	2.45	2.38	2.31	2.23	2.19	2.15	2.10	2.06	2.01	1.96
18	2.41	2.34	2.27	2.19	2.15	2.11	2.06	2.02	1.97	1.92
19	2.38	2.31	2.23	2.16	2.11	2.07	2.03	1.98	1.93	1.88
20	2.35	2.28	2.20	2.12	2.08	2.04	1.99	1.95	1.90	1.84
21	2.32	2.25	2.18	2.10	2.05	2.01	1.96	1.92	1.87	1.81
22	2.30	2.23	2.15	2.07	2.03	1.98	1.94	1.89	1.84	1.78
23	2.27	2.20	2.13	2.05	2.01	1.96	1.91	1.86	1.81	1.76
24	2.25	2.18	2.11	2.03	1.98	1.94	1.89	1.84	1.79	1.73
25	2.24	2.16	2.09	2.01	1.96	1.92	1.87	1.82	1.77	1.71
26	2.22	2.15	2.07	1.99	1.95	1.90	1.85	1.80	1.75	1.69
27	2.20	2.13	2.06	1.97	1.93	1.88	1.84	1.79	1.73	1.67
28	2.19	2.12	2.04	1.96	1.91	1.87	1.82	1.77	1.71	1.65
29	2.18	2.10	2.03	1.94	1.90	1.85	1.81	1.75	1.70	1.64
30	2.16	2.09	2.01	1.93	1.89	1.84	1.79	1.74	1.68	1.62
40	2.08	2.00	1.92	1.84	1.79	1.74	1.69	1.64	1.58	1.51
60	1.99	1.92	1.84	1.75	1.70	1.65	1.59	1.53	1.47	1.39
120	1.91	1.83	1.75	1.66	1.10	1.55	1.50	1.43	1.35	1.25
Infinity	1.83	1.75	1.67	1.57	1.52	1.46	1.39	1.32	1.22	1.00